

THE ROLE OF TALENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A PERSON'S COMMUNICATION STYLE

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Abstract. *In this article, the role of talent in the development of a person's communication style and the culture of communication is the most necessary factor for a person. The main reason why a person is called a product of social relations means that he is always in the circle of people, in the framework of interaction with them. This indicates that one of the most leading and influential activities of a person is communication. It is an important task for teachers and psychologists to identify gifted children in time and direct their talents to a specific field.*

Key words: *Personality, communication, talent, talent, perception, memory, thinking, ability, natural, special, pedagogical abilities: a) didactic abilities; b) academic skills ; c) perceptive abilities.*

"РОЛЬ ТАЛАНТА В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ СТИЛЯ ОБЩЕНИЯ ЧЕЛОВЕКА"

Аннотация. *В этой статье рассматривается роль таланта в развитии стиля общения человека, а культура общения является наиболее необходимым фактором для человека. Основная причина, по которой человека называют продуктом социальных отношений, означает, что он всегда находится в кругу людей, в рамках взаимодействия с ними. Это указывает на то, что одним из наиболее ведущих и влиятельных видов деятельности человека является общение. Для педагогов и психологов важной задачей является своевременное выявление одаренных детей и направление их талантов в определенную область.*

Ключевые слова: *Личность, коммуникация, талант, одаренность, восприятие, память, мышление, способности, природные, специальные, педагогические способности: a) дидактические способности; б) академические навыки; в) перцептивные способности.*

Communication is one of the primary activities manifested in the process of individual development of a person, and it is one of the strong needs of a person - to be a person, to speak like people, to understand them, to love them, to coordinate mutual relations. originates. A person starts his development by mastering this type of activity and creates the ground for perfect mastery of other types of activity through speech (verbal) and non-verbal means (non-verbal). Any activity requires people to get along with each other , transfer various information to each other, and exchange ideas. Therefore, the position of each person in society, the success of his work, and his reputation are directly related to his ability to communicate.

Communication is an important condition of human life and activity. It is through communication that people are able to master their nature and work together to meet their individual needs. In the process of communication, certain images and models of human behavior are formed, and then they enter into a person. The ability to analyze and evaluate a person's thinking, world and self-image is formed in the process of communication.

The main goal of the psychology of communication is, first of all, the formation of speech culture in young people. Also, during the training process, it is necessary to inculcate

communication culture and manners in the future specialists, to improve mutual relations in groups and teams by forming communication.

The main tasks of communication psychology are expressed in the following:

- 1) studying the laws of interpersonal interaction and communication in the process of cooperative activity;
- 2) to analyze the views of Eastern scholars about communication;
- 3) emphasizing the availability of communication opportunities encouraging the student to be active;
- 4) formation of communication aimed at activating the professional ability of students;
- 5) gain the role of communication in coordinating interpersonal relations;
- 6) consideration of some consequences of interaction.
- 7) In addition, communication is performed in human social life

There are also tasks (function). Communication functions are diverse, and according to the most common classification, they are as follows: (classification proposed by BF Lomov):

1. Informational-communicative function — the task of providing information exchange. Information exchange is carried out through various symbols and systems. Usually, verbal (in which speech is used as a sign system) and non-verbal (in which a non-verbal sign system is used) communication is distinguished. Nonverbal communication consists of several forms:

- kinetics (gesture, mime, pantomime);
- paralinguistics (sound localizations, pauses);
- proxemics (measures of distance and time);
- visual communication (communication through the eyes);
- such physical contact).

Sometimes the smells of individuals in communication are also evaluated as a unique system of signs.

2. Regulatory-communicative function - the task of ensuring the regulation (management) of the interlocutors' behavior. In the process of communication, people influence each other's motives, goals, decision-making in verbal, physical, non-verbal ways, encourage and control their actions, stimulate and correct each other's behavior. can show.

3. Affective-communicative function is the task of ensuring the regulation (management) of the human emotional sphere. Communication is the most important determinant of human emotional states. Because different emotional states appear and change in the process of communication.

Communication forms a person as a person, gives him the opportunity to acquire his own characteristics, interests, habits, inclinations, to learn the norms and forms of moral behavior, to determine the goals of life and to choose the right and inexpensive ways to achieve them. Communication is one of the first forms of activity that is genetically manifested in a child. Therefore, the uniqueness of a person's social existence is manifested in communication. It includes many different relationships with people: parents, teachers, acquaintances, strangers, peers, juniors, friends. The child chooses friends, he seeks to communicate with a certain circle of people, influences others. He works as an organizer and executor in the most diverse team.

Communication activity helps to form important aspects of a person, such as humanity, sensitivity, care, sense of responsibility for oneself, and one's behavior in front of the surrounding people.

Communication mostly starts with the family. If communication is formed in children from a small age, they will grow receptive to the relationship. Since they are small, you need to talk to them more. Children are curious. If children are supported by their parents, they will be able to express their opinion and be able to communicate quickly. If he is teased by his parents, he grows shy. More trainings and activities should be organized for children. As a result of this, children will develop a high level of communication.

The main reason for the inability to communicate is the wrong attitude towards oneself and the people around one due to excessive or low self-esteem. There are ways to prevent this, and mainly, giving importance to the following has a positive effect: 1) organization of humanitarian relations between all members of the communication process through the communication system, creation of an opportunity to compare the emotional environment;

2) implementation of activities aimed at ensuring a comfortable position of each member in the system of internal relations in communication; 3) to organize special trainings for the acquisition of information about the features, manners, methods and forms of human communication. 4) it is necessary to create a system of business games, psychodrama, and training aimed at interpersonal relations and communication methods.

A gifted child is a person who has more mental abilities than his peers, mentally, spiritually, physically, and has priority characteristics compared to other children [8]. Gifted children have their own characteristics, we will list them one by one below:

- He starts speaking early from a young age, his vocabulary is formed early;
- quickly remembers information and has the ability to sort them;
- will have the technique of using existing knowledge;
- looks at the environment with curiosity;
- learns topics easily;
- strong imagination, etc.[7].

There are a number of methods for mentally correct communication skills in gifted children, in particular:

- formation of self-confidence in the child;
- ensuring that the child communicates with people;
- forming a view of the environment in relation to analysis;
- to give the child an understanding of the positive and negative points in the relationship, etc.

- As a conclusion, we can say that the role of talent in the development of a person's communication style parents, teachers and psychologists are of great importance in their identification and correct psychocorrection.

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